

Evaluating Fine-Tuned LLMs for AI Text Detection

This Zenodo record contains metadata for the publication:

Title: Evaluating Fine-Tuned LLMs for AI Text Detection

Authors: Marco Murgia, Diego Reforgiato Recupero, Georgios Spathoulas

DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-00642-4_17

Note:

The full text of this publication is not available on Zenodo due to copyright restrictions.

Please refer to the official publication via the publisher's website.

This record is intended for citation and indexing purposes only.